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Table of Contents

Annex A	Systematic literature review	1
A.1.	Protocol	1
A.1.1.	Background	1
A.1.2.	Review questions	2
A.1.3.	Criteria for including studies	2
A.1.4.	Criteria for excluding studies	3
A.1.5.	Information sources	3
A.1.6.	Search strategy	3
A.1.7.	Review methods	4
A.1.7.1.	Selection of the studies	4
A.1.7.2.	Data extraction	4
A.1.8.	Analysis and reporting	4
A.2.	Results	5
A.2.1.	SLR 1 – Risk of vertical transmission	5
A.2.1.1.	Methods	5
A.2.1.2.	Results	6
A.2.1.3.	Discussion and conclusion	11
A.2.2.	SLR 2 – Risk mitigation measures and critical control points	13
A.2.2.1.	Methods	13
A.2.2.2.	Results	14
A.2.2.3.	Discussion and conclusion	16

Annex A Systematic literature review

A.1. Protocol

A.1.1. Background

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has been requested to provide scientific and technical assistance to the European Commission (EC) regarding the risk of viral haemorrhagic septicaemia (VHS), infectious haematopoietic necrosis (IHN) and infection with HPR-deleted infectious salmon anaemia virus (HPR-deleted ISAV) introduction in areas declared free of those diseases related to the introduction of fertilised eggs and gametes of listed species originating from areas which are not free of those diseases. The current protocol describes the methodology of the two systematic literature reviews (SLRs) that were conducted to meet the following objectives (i) to assess the existing evidence on the risk of vertical transmission of VHS, IHN and HPR-deleted ISAV (SLR 1) (ii) to assess the existing evidence on the effectiveness of risk mitigation measure (RMMs) conditions provided for in the draft new Chapter 4.Z. of the World

Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) Aquatic Code and any others identified via the literature to prevent VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV spread/introduction via movement of fertilised eggs or gametes from a non-free to a free area (SLR 2); (iii) and to identify the critical points to be controlled at the establishments where the fertilised eggs and gametes of aquaculture animals are produced to ensure early detection and prevent further spread of VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV (SLR 2).

A.1.2. Review questions

The specific objective of SLR 1 is to answer the following review question:

- What is the existing evidence on the risk of vertical transmission of VHSV, IHNV, HPR-deleted ISAV in listed species, including the potential differences in transmission by eggs, sperm and gametes?

The specific objective of SLR 2 is to answer the two following review questions:

1. What is the existing evidence on the effectiveness of RMMs to prevent VHSV, IHNV or HPR-deleted ISAV spread/introduction via movement of eggs, sperm or gametes from a non-free to a free area?
2. What are the critical points to be controlled at the establishments where the eggs, sperm and gametes of aquaculture animals are produced to ensure early detection and prevent further spread of VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV?

A.1.3. Criteria for including studies

The two systematic literature reviews address the above-mentioned review questions and for SLR1 use the **PECO** (**P**opulation – **E**xposure – **C**omparison – **O**utcome) and for SLR2 the **PICO** (**P**opulation – **I**ntervention – **C**omparison – **O**utcome) formats to frame inclusion criteria (Table A.1).

TABLE A.1 PECO and PICO formats for the two systematic literature reviews.

SLR 1		SLR 2	
Parameter	Inclusion criteria	Parameter	Inclusion criteria
Population	Listed fish species *	Population	Eggs, sperm or gametes from listed fish species *
Exposure	Exposure to one of the pathogens of interest: VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV	Intervention	1. RMM to prevent VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV transmission 2. Critical control point during production
Comparison	Potential differences in transmission between eggs, sperm or gametes	Comparison	NA
Outcome	Any outcome related to the risk of transmission of the pathogen via eggs, sperm or gametes	Outcome	Any outcome related to the effectiveness of the intervention (as defined above) (e.g. pathogen inactivation measured by decrease in viral load)

***VHS**: Herring (*Clupea* spp.), whitefish (*Coregonus* spp.), pike (*Esox lucius*), haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*), Pacific cod (*Gadus macrocephalus*), Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*), Pacific salmon (*Oncorhynchus* spp.), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), rockling (*Onos mustelus*), brown trout (*Salmo trutta*), turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*), sprat (*Sprattus sprattus*), grayling (*Thymallus thymallus*), olive flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*), marble trout (*Salmo marmoratus*), lake trout (*Salvelinus namaycush*), wrasse (*Labridae* spp.), lumpfish (*Cyclopteridae* spp.); **IHN**: Chum salmon (*Oncorhynchus keta*), coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*), Masou salmon (*Oncorhynchus masou*),

rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), sockeye salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*), pink salmon (*Oncorhynchus rhodurus*), chinook salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*), Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), lake trout (*Salvelinus namaycush*), marble trout (*Salmo marmoratus*), brook trout (*Salvelinus fontinalis*), arctic charr (*Salvelinus alpinus*), whitespotted charr (*Salvelinus leucomaenis*); **HPR-deleted ISAV**: Rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), brown and sea trout (*Salmo trutta*)

Abbreviation: NA: not applicable; RMM: risk mitigation measure

In line with this, the following criteria for inclusion will be used to select studies to be included in the SLRs:

- 1 Primary research publication
- 2 Study on VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV
- 3 Study on any of the listed species (SLR1)
- 4 Study concerning eggs, sperm or gametes of the listed species (SLR2)
- 5 Study evaluating the risk of transmission of the pathogen to eggs, sperm or gametes (SLR1)
- 6 Study evaluating a RMM or a critical control point (SLR2)
- 7 Any study design
- 8 Any geographic location
- 9 Published in English

A.1.4. Criteria for excluding studies

The references will be excluded from the review if they meet one or more of following criteria:

- 1 Published after search date (25/10/2024)
- 2 Review papers. However original studies included in the review papers complying with the inclusion/exclusion criteria will be included.

A.1.5. Information sources

The literature search will be conducted in MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Scopus to obtain peer-reviewed, scientific publications related to the review. In addition, the reference list of relevant studies retrieved from the electronic database search will be hand searched to identify additional studies, and grey literature will be searched using a generic search engine (e.g. Google Scholar) and target expressions.

A.1.6. Search strategy

The following broad search strategy will be used in PubMed (Table A.2):

TABLE A.2 Description of the search string used in PubMed.

#	Search string	# of results (25/10/2024)
1	"Viral Haemorrhagic Septicaemia"[All Fields] OR "Viral Hemorrhagic Septicaemia"[All Fields] OR "Infectious Haematopoietic Necrosis"[All Fields] OR "Infectious Hematopoietic Necrosis"[All Fields] OR "Infectious salmon anaemia"[All Fields] OR "Infectious salmon anemia"[All Fields] OR "VHS"[All Fields] OR "IHN"[All Fields] OR "ISAV"[All Fields] OR "Egtved disease"[All Fields] OR "Egtved virus"[All Fields])	4,020

2	#1 AND "egg"[All Fields] OR "sperm s"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoa"[MeSH Terms] OR "spermatozoa"[All Fields] OR "sperm"[All Fields] OR "sperms"[All Fields] OR "gamete*"[All Fields] OR "milt*"[All Fields] OR "oocyte*"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoa"[MeSH Terms] OR "spermatozoa"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoon"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoa s"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoas"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoon s"[All Fields] OR "spermatozoons"[All Fields] OR "germinal"[All Fields] OR "germinative"[All Fields] OR "vertical transmission"[All Fields] OR "reproduction"[MeSH Terms] OR "reproduction"[All Fields] OR "reproductions"[All Fields] OR "reproductive"[All Fields] OR "reproductively"[All Fields] OR "reproductives"[All Fields] OR "reproductivity"[All Fields] OR "reproduction"[MeSH Terms] OR "reproduction"[All Fields] OR "reproductions"[All Fields] OR "reproductive"[All Fields] OR "reproductively"[All Fields] OR "reproductives"[All Fields] OR "reproductivity"[All Fields] OR "ovum"[MeSH Terms] OR "ovum"[All Fields] OR "ova"[All Fields]	92
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A.1.7. Review methods

A.1.7.1. Selection of the studies

In the first review phase, the resulting lists of references will be exported to Rayyan¹ to proceed with duplicate removal, as well as the title, abstract and keywords screening and study selection. The complete selection process will be documented in an Endnote file, containing folders that reflect the selection criteria.

A.1.7.2. Data extraction

In the first review phase, the resulting lists of references will be exported to Rayyan² to proceed with duplicate removal, as well as the title, abstract and keywords screening and study selection. The complete selection process will be documented in an Endnote file, containing folders that reflect the selection criteria.

A.1.8. Analysis and reporting

The extracted data will be summarized in tables and narratively. The report will be divided by pathogen and matrice (eggs, sperm or gametes) for SLR1 and by objective, and intervention measure type for SLR2.

During the selection process, the results of the literature search will be imported into Endnote where a clear track of the selection process will be maintained, and the flow of publications will be noted. Based on these numbers, a flowchart of the studies selected in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)³ guidelines will be prepared for use in the report.

¹ <https://rayyan.qcri.org>

² <https://rayyan.qcri.org>

³ <https://www.prisma-statement.org/>

A.2. Results

The current report summarizes the results of the two SLRs.

A.2.1. SLR 1 – Risk of vertical transmission

A.2.1.1. Methods

As described in the protocol above, the specific objective of this SLR was to answer the following review question: What is the existing evidence on the risk of vertical transmission of VHS virus (VHSV), IHN virus (IHNV), infection with HPR-deleted ISAV in listed species, including the potential differences in transmission by fertilised eggs or gametes?

Vertical transmission is defined here as the transfer of viable virus particles (i.e. positive to one of the recommended test of the EURLFISH diagnostic manual or the disease specific chapter of WOAHA aquatic manual) from parents to progeny. True vertical transmission is considered that which cannot be prevented by decontamination of the eggs. All other vertical transmission (which can be prevented by disinfection treatments/measures) is considered "egg surface associated transfer". Both true vertical transmission and egg surface associated transfer of infection from parents to progeny are here considered.

The database searches were carried out on 25 October 2024 within MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Scopus. After adding records retrieved through reference list checking and hand searching via Google Scholar, a total of 2,435 unique references were identified. From these references, 31 were finally selected, for data extraction. The full selection process is displayed in **Figure A.1**.

The following data were extracted: Study period, Study type (experimental/field), Pathogen (IHNV, VHSV, ISAV), Fish species, Matrice (eggs/sperm/gametes), Sample size, Outcome description, Outcome value, Short conclusion.

FIGURE A.1 PRISMA diagram describing the different steps of SLR 1.

* Records identified through reference list checking and hand searching

A.2.1.2. Results

The references included for data extraction are displayed in **Table A.3**. In the results section, the references are described by pathogen and in a chronological order.

TABLE A.3 Included references for vertical transmission of VHSV, IHNV and ISAV.

Pathogen	Fertilised eggs	Non-fertilised eggs	Sperm
<i>Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus</i>	Ahmadivand et al., 2021; Ghittino, 1965; Jørgensen, 1974; Oidtmann et al., 2014	Al-Hussinee & Lumsden, 2011; Chaves-Pozo et al., 2010; Jensen, 1965; Munro & Gregory, 2010	Eaton et al., 1991; Mulcahy & Pascho, 1984
<i>Infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus</i>	Ahmadivand et al., 2021; Amend, 1975; Meyers, 1998; Mulcahy & Bauersfeld, 1983; Mulcahy & Pascho, 1985; Oidtmann et al., 2014; Ratliff et al., 1982; Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1993; Yoshimizu et al., 1989	Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1989	Eaton et al., 1991; Meyers et al., 1990; Mulcahy et al., 1987; Mulcahy & Pascho, 1984; Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1989
<i>Infectious salmon anaemia virus</i>	Christiansen et al., 2021; Melville & Griffiths, 1999; Nylund et al., 2019; Nylund et al., 1999; Oidtmann et al., 2014; Plarre et al., 2012; Polinski et al., 2024; Thorud, 1988; Vike et al., 2009	Marshall et al., 2014; Nylund et al., 1995	Not available

Viral Haemorrhagic Septicaemia Virus

Among the 31 studies included in the SLR, 10 investigated the risk associated with fertilised eggs, non- fertilised eggs or sperm in the transmission of VHS virus (VHSV).

Fertilised eggs

Ghittino (1965) described a case of VHSV infection that occurred in an Italian rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) hatchery without any previous history of VHS, where the infected fingerlings had hatched from eyed eggs imported from a hatchery where VHS was endemic.

Despite that P.E.V. Jørgensen (1974) isolated in one occasion VHSV from freshly stripped eggs, he concluded that the risk of vertical transmission was negligible since if kept in virus free running water the virus was no longer detectable in 7-8.000 eggs 5 days after inoculation with 1.000 TCID₅₀ VHSV/egg. And commented that until 1974 European trout fertilised eggs have been exported to all parts of the world without VHS being introduced into any country outside Europe.

In the context of an expert consultation on risk factors for the introduction of infectious pathogens into fish farms (Oidtmann et al., 2014), the experts estimated that the risk that disinfected rainbow trout fertilised eggs from a subclinically infected source site would lead to VHSV infections at a receiving site was only of one out of 100 consignments.

A phylogenetic analysis conducted in Iran among rainbow trout VHSV isolates originating from clinical outbreaks suggested that the pathogen had been imported from Europe, most likely via imported embryonated eggs (Ahmadivand et al., 2021).

Non-fertilised eggs

Jensen (1965) demonstrated in an experiment that VHSV isolated from rainbow trout could be transmitted to primary monolayer cultures of cell prepared from immature rainbow trout ovaries.

Munro and Gregory (2010) described an experiment in which rainbow trout sperm, non-fertilised eggs or both were infected with VHSV. As the fertilised eggs and fry turned out to be negative to both virus isolation and real-time PCR, the authors concluded that the risk associated with VHSV vertical transmission is low.

Chaves Pozo et al. (2010) conducted an experiment in rainbow trout and showed that contrarily to infectious pancreatic necrosis virus (IPNV) which is known to be transmitted vertically, VHSV is able to replicate within the ovarian tissue, which triggers a strong chemokine response that prevents vertical transmission through oocytes.

Al-Hussinee and Lumsden (2011) detected VHSV IVb RNA using immunohistochemistry in the ovary of experimentally infected rainbow trout; abundant staining was present in the mesovarium, with lesser amounts in both the ooplasm and germinal vesicles of immature oocytes.

Milt

Mulcahy and Pascho (1984) observed no adsorption of VHSV to milt of chinook salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*), unlike IHN virus (IHNV).

Eaton et al. (1991) isolated VHSV in sperm pools from wild Coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus Kisutch*).

All the available evidence concerning VHSV has been summarized in Table A.4.

TABLE A.4 Available evidence for vertical transmission of VHSV.

Matrice	Study type	Mitigation measure	Evidence of VT	Reference
fertilised eggs	field	not reported	possible	Ahmadivand et al., 2021; Ghittino, 1965
	experimental	not reported	no /unlikely	Jørgensen, 1974
	expert consultation	iodine disinfection	possible	Oidtmann et al., 2014
non-fertilised eggs	experimental	not reported	possible	(l-Hussinee & Lumsden, 2011; Jensen, 1965
		not reported	no	Chaves-Pozo et al., 2010; Munro & Gregory, 2010
milt	field	not reported	possible	Eaton et al., 1991
	experimental	not reported	no	Mulcahy, Jenes et al. 1984

Abbreviations: VT: vertical transmission

Infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus

Among the 31 studies included in the SLR, 14 references concerned the potential transmission of IHNV with fertilised eggs, non-fertilised eggs or sperm.

Fertilised eggs

Amend (1975) carried out an experiment in rainbow trout and showed that although IHNV could be isolated from ovarian fluid from infected carrier females, the virus could not be detected in embryos or fry when the eggs had been incubated several weeks in virus-free water.

In an experimental study, Ratliff et al. (1982) isolated IHNV from steelhead (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fertilised eggs despite saline rinsing during spawning, disinfection with iodophor, and incubation and raising in virus-free water.

Mulcahy and Bauersfeld (1983) studied the effect of sockeye salmon (*Onchorynchus nerka*) egg density in streamside incubation boxes. IHNV was isolated from fry originating from the high egg density boxes despite the fact that the fertilised eggs had been rinsed and treated with an iodophor solution.

Mulcahy and Pascho (1985) investigated the potential for IHNV to be transmitted from infected sockeye salmon broodstock collected in the field to progeny. The authors reported that only a small proportion of eggs and fry were infected with IHNV, therefore this might explain why vertical transmission is hard to demonstrate through a small-scale experiment.

An experimental study conducted by Yoshimizu et al. (Yoshimizu et al., 1989) observed no mortality and no trace of IHNV inside or on the surface of fertilised eggs from IHNV-infected gametes (non-fertilised egg-contaminated, sperm-contaminated, non-fertilised egg and sperm-contaminated) from masu (*Oncorhynchus masou*) and chum salmon (*Oncorhynchus kela*). On the other hand, the results confirmed the susceptibility of salmon to IHNV from the eyed egg stage onwards. The authors concluded that direct vertical transmission of IHNV to salmon progeny was doubtful since the virus seems unable to survive in fertilised eggs before the eyed stage.

Yoshimizu et al. (1993) reported that IHNV was isolated at a hatchery in masu salmon ovarian fluid, with an incidence of infection of 60%. The entire facilities received an annual disinfection with chlorine, while the fertilised eggs were treated with iodophore. As a results, IHNV has not been isolated again at hatchery.

Traxler et al. (1997) conducted an experiment crossing IHNV infected adult sockeye salmon and exposing gametes to the virus. IHNV was not isolated in milt nor in any of the eggs or fry. Similarly, fertilised eggs water-hardened in the presence of the virus yielded virus-free progeny.

Meyers (1998) reported an outbreak of IHNV infection in sockeye salmon at an Alaskan hatchery. After ruling out all potential horizontal transmission sources, the study concludes that internal contamination of the egg is the only plausible route for the observed infection, although vertical transmission is a rare event.

A phylogenetic analysis conducted in Iran among rainbow trout IHNV isolates originating from clinical outbreaks suggested that the pathogen had been imported from Europe, most likely via imported embryonated eggs (Ahmadivand et al., 2021).

In the context of an expert consultation on risk factors for introduction of infectious pathogens into fish farms (Oidtmann et al., 2014), the experts estimated that five out of 100 consignments of disinfected rainbow trout eggs from a subclinically infected source site could lead to infections of IHNV at receiving sites.

Non-fertilised eggs

In an experimental study conducted by Yoshimizu et al. (1989), no mortality was observed, and IHNV was not isolated from inside nor from the surface of fertilised eggs originating from IHNV-

infected masu and chum salmon gametes (non-fertilised egg-contaminated, sperm-contaminated, non-fertilised egg and sperm- contaminated).

Traxler et al. (1997) conducted an experiment crossing IHNV infected adult sockeye salmon and exposing non-fertilised eggs to the virus. IHNV was not isolated in milt nor in any of the fertilised eggs or fry.

Milt

Mulcahy and Pascho (1984) showed that the IHNV could be adsorbed to milt of chinook salmon in less than one minute, suggesting thereby that vertical transmission may occur via milt which would act as a vehicle for the entry of the virus into the egg.

Mulcahy et al. (1987) observed lower viral incidence and titres in milt from sockeye salmon and steelhead trout than in other organs such as the kidney and the spleen.

Eaton et al. (1991) isolated IHNV in sperm pools from wild Coho salmon.

An experimental study conducted by Yoshimizu et al. (1989) observed no mortality and IHNV was not isolated from the inside nor from the surface of fertile eggs from IHNV-infected masu and chum salmon gametes (non-fertilised egg-contaminated, sperm-contaminated, non-fertilised egg and milt- contaminated).

Meyers et al. (1990) estimated the prevalence of IHNV-positive milt from Alaskan Sockeye salmon using plaque assay to be between 10% and 29%.

Traxler et al. (1997) conducted an experiment crossing IHNV infected adult sockeye salmon and exposing gametes to the virus. IHNV was not isolated from sperm nor from any of the fertilised eggs or fry.

All the available evidence concerning IHNV has been summarized in Table A.5.

TABLE A.5 Available evidence for vertical transmission of IHNV.

Matrice	Study type	Mitigation measure	Evidence of VT	Reference
fertilised eggs	field	not reported	possible	(Ahmadvand et al., 2021; Mulcahy & Pascho, 1985)
		iodophor disinfection	yes	(Meyers, 1998)
			no	(Yoshimizu et al., 1993)
	experimental	not reported	no	(Amend, 1975; Yoshimizu et al., 1989)
		iodophor disinfection	yes	(Mulcahy & Bauersfeld, 1983; Ratliff et al., 1982)
			no	(Traxler et al., 1997)
	expert consultation	iodophor disinfection	possible	(Oidtmann et al., 2014)
non-fertilised eggs	experimental	not reported	no	(Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1989)
sperm	field	not reported	possible	(Eaton et al., 1991; Meyers et al., 1990; Mulcahy et al., 1987)
	experimental	not reported	possible	(Mulcahy & Pascho, 1985)
			no	(Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1989)

Abbreviations: VT: vertical transmission

Infectious salmon anaemia virus

Among the 31 studies included in the SLR, 11 studies concerned the potential transmission of ISA virus (ISAV) by fertilised eggs, non-fertilised eggs or milt.

Fertilised eggs

Thorud and Vik (Thorud, 1988) failed to demonstrate vertical transmission as the authors observed no sign of the disease and no mortality among Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) that had been injected ISAV-infected fertilised egg homogenate.

Nylund et al. (Nylund et al., 1999) described an outbreak of ISAV that occurred during first feeding in Atlantic salmon fry which might suggest that ISAV survived in ovarian fluids or entered egg at fertilisation. The presence of ISAV in larvae was shown with the help of cell cultures, IFAT and RT-PCR and transmission electron microscopy. The fry originated from fertilised eggs that had been disinfected according to the guidelines, per the responsible veterinarian. A total of six out of 22 fish larvae were shown to be positive by RT-PCR.

Melville and Griffiths (1999) found that the ISAV was not detected in disinfected eyed eggs from experimentally infected Atlantic salmon with ISAV-RT-PCR positive ovarian fluid and no mortality occurred among fish injected with egg homogenates derived from ISA-positive fish.

In the context of an expert consultation on risk factors for introduction of infectious pathogens into fish farms (Oidtmann et al., 2014), it was estimated by the experts that 0.01 out of 100 consignments of disinfected Atlantic salmon embryonated eggs from a subclinically infected source site would lead to infections of ISAV at receiving sites.

Three studies conducting phylogenetic analysis (Plarre et al., 2012; Vike et al., 2009; Plarre et al., 2012; Nylund et al., 2019) concluded that the most likely explanation for the emergence of ISAV in Chile was vertical transmission since the country imported at that time a lot of Atlantic salmon fertilised eggs from Norway. On the contrary, another genetic analysis (Christiansen et al., 2021) demonstrated little genetic link between the nonvirulent HPRO ISAV (the putative progenitor for virulent-ISAV) found in Icelandic and Norwegian broodfish and their progeny in the Faroese smolt farms, thus suggesting that HPRO was not transmitted vertically.

Polinski et al. (2024) didn't find any ISAV HPRO using RT-PCR in any of the fertilised eggs and progeny collected from confirmed HPRO ISAV infected Atlantic salmon broodstock, and concluded that HPRO ISAV has a limited likelihood for vertical parent-to-offspring transmission in cultured Atlantic salmon.

Non-fertilised eggs

Nylund et al. (1995) observed using transmission electron microscopy, the presence of free ISAV particles in blood vessels from gonads from infected Atlantic salmon; the authors pinpointed that the primary target tissues for the virus was the vascular endothelium.

Marshall et al. (2014) recovered an epizootic virulent variant of ISAV (HPR-3), from the ovarian fluid and the interior of non-fertilised eggs of naturally infected Atlantic salmon; it was also observed that the viruses recovered from both fractions were highly infective to a susceptible fish cell line, which is suggestive of functional vertical transmission.

Milt

No reference was retrieved for the risk posed by milt.

All the available evidence concerning ISAV has been summarized in **Table A.6**.

TABLE A.6 Available evidence for vertical transmission of ISAV.

Matrice	Study type	Mitigation measure	Evidence of VT	Reference
fertilised eggs	field	not reported	no	Christiansen et al., 2021
			possible	Nylund et al., 1999; Plarre et al., 2012; Vike et al., 2009
		iodophor disinfection	no	Olinski et al., 2024
			possible*	Nylund et al., 1999
	experimental	not reported	no	Thorud, 1988
		iodophor disinfection	no	Melville & Griffiths, 1999
	expert consultation	iodophor disinfection	possible	Oidtman et al., 2014
non-fertilised eggs	field	not reported	possible	Nylund et al., 1995
		not reported	yes	Marshall et al., 2014

Abbreviations: VT: vertical transmission

*study conclusions not clear (see Discussion section)

A.2.1.3. Discussion and conclusion

Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus

Several phylogenetic analyses showed that outbreaks occurring in regions with no prior history of VHS were most likely originating from embryonated eggs imported from endemic regions. On the other hand, research indicates that while VHSV might contaminate the egg surface, it seems not able to survive the egg incubation period (Bovo et al., 2005). Indeed, in most cases, when fertilised eggs undergo recommended disinfection procedures (WOAH, 2024), the virus is not transmitted vertically or only extremely rarely. In line with this, there have been cases where the introduction of untreated green eggs from infected farms during the incubation phase of a VHSV outbreak has led to subsequent VHS outbreaks (H. Korsholm, Danish Veterinary Services) (European Food Safety Authority 2007). Several reviews (Bovo et al., 2005; Espen Rimstad et al., 2019) mention a study conducted by Vestergård Jørgensen (1974) in which viable VHSV could only be detected 3h and a half after fertilisation of naturally infected non-disinfected eggs. Referring also to unpublished field observations, this author concluded that the virus may be present as contaminant on the egg surface, but that it apparently does not survive the egg incubation period (Jørgensen, 1974). Chavez-Pozo et al. (2010) showed that VHSV is able to replicate in the ovarian tissue, which triggers a strong immune response, thereby preventing vertical transmission of the pathogen. It has also been suggested that antiviral factors within yolk components most likely inactivate virus or interrupt the replication (Al-Hussiney et al., 2010). These conclusions are supported by the findings of an expert consultation (Oidtman et al., 2014), which considers the risk of introducing VHSV to a disease-free farm through disinfected rainbow trout eggs sourced from an infected site to be very low.

The virus has been found in sperm (Eaton et al., 1991) from wild coho salmon, but Mulcahy and Pascho (1984) were unable to demonstrate the adsorption of the virus to Chinook salmon sperm.

In the literature review conducted in the context of the EU FP6 project Fish Egg Trade report 'Hazard identification for vertical transfer of fish disease agents' published in 2005 (Bovo et al., 2005), it was concluded that there was so far no evidence of true vertical transmission of VHSV.

In conclusion, we did not retrieve any study that demonstrates true vertical transmission via fertilised eggs or gametes. The available data indicate that, while contamination of fertilised egg surfaces by VHSV may be observed, the virus is normally not transmitted vertically if appropriate disinfection of the eggs is implemented.

Infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus

Although several studies pointed out the presence of IHNV in progeny originating from eggs (Mulcahy and Bauersfeld, 1983; Mulcahy and Pascho, 1985; Meyers, 1998; Meyers et al., 1990), most studies indicate that IHNV-infected parents do not produce IHNV-infected offspring when the eggs were raised in virus-free water or underwent disinfection with an iodophor solution (Wingfield and Chan, 1970; Amend, 1975; Ratliff et al., 1982; Traxler et al., 1997; Bovo et al., 2005; Oidtmann et al., 2014).

Experimental studies failed to demonstrate vertical transmission via gametes (Traxler et al., 1997; Yoshimizu et al., 1989). It has been suggested that components of the egg yolk may inhibit viral replication. The capacity of IHNV to replicate following injection into the egg appears to be linked to the progression of embryonic development, as it correlates with a reduction in yolk components (Yoshimizu et al., 1989; Bovo et al., 2005).

It has been demonstrated that IHNV could be quickly adsorbed to the surface membrane of steelhead trout and Chinook salmon sperm (Mulcahy and Pascho, 1984), suggesting thereby that sperm-attached IHNV originating either from the male fish or from infected ovarian fluid could deliver the virus directly into the egg during fertilisation. However, the contamination of salmon sperm with IHNV did not result in the infection of eggs in the study from Yoshimizu et al. (Yoshimizu et al., 1989), and there is no direct evidence that sperm can transmit IHNV into eggs (Espen Rimstad et al., 2019).

The conclusion of the EU FP6 project Fish Egg Trade report 'Hazard identification for vertical transfer of fish disease agents' (Bovo et al., 2005) was that, based on experiences in the laboratory and in the field, the risk of true vertical transmission of IHNV is negligible.

To conclude, there are currently few studies providing evidence for true vertical transmission of IHNV. Indeed, we only retrieved one field study and two experiments in which IHNV was detected from fertilised eggs despite iodine disinfection (Ratliff et al., 1982; Mulcahy & Bauersfeld, 1983; Meyers, 1998). There is also no clear evidence concerning the possibility of vertical transmission posed by non-fertilised eggs or sperm.

Infectious salmon anemia virus

Several phylogenetic analyses showed that the most likely explanation for the emergence of ISAV in Chile was vertical transmission since the country imported at that time a lot of Atlantic salmon embryos from Norway. On the other hand, it was described that, until 1998, Chile imported millions of Atlantic salmon eggs from Norway without requirements that the eggs should be derived from ISA free broodstock. Despite this, ISA has not been reported in the progeny of Atlantic salmon in Chile until 2007 (Bovo et al., 2005; Godoy et al., 2008).

The possibility that the ISAV outbreak which occurred during first feeding of Atlantic salmon fry (Nylund et al., 1999) might be a case of vertical transmission was discussed without a definite conclusion. In addition, no ISAV was isolated from extensive samplings carried out by the veterinary authorities on a later stage in the same population (Bovo et al., 2005). Similarly, several experimental studies failed to demonstrate vertical transmission via eggs (Thorud, 1988; Melville and Griffiths, 1999; Polinski et al., 2024).

The findings of the EU FP6 project Fish Egg Trade report 'Hazard identification for vertical transfer of fish disease agents' (Bovo et al., 2005) indicated that there was no hard evidence for the vertical transmission inside the gamete or the egg, and vertical transmission is obviously insignificant in the epidemiology of the infection.

However, an HPR-deleted ISAV isolate from Chile has been since then recovered from the interior of eggs originating from naturally infected Atlantic salmon, suggesting the possibility of vertical transmission of the variant to fry and juvenile salmon (Marshall et al., 2014).

In conclusion, we retrieved only two studies that suggested that true vertical transmission might be possible. A field study in which fish larvae originating from fertilised eggs that had been disinfected were found to be ISAV positive by RT-PCR (Nylund et al., 1999). However, the abovementioned conclusion of this study is not clear. Another study recovered highly infective ISAV from the interior of non-fertilised eggs of naturally infected Atlantic salmon (Marshall et al., 2014). Thus, the evidence for fertilised and non-fertilised eggs is currently limited. No conclusion can be drawn regarding the risk of vertical transmission through sperm as no relevant data were retrieved.

A.2.2. SLR 2 – Risk mitigation measures and critical control points

A.2.2.1. Methods

As described in the protocol, the specific objective of this SLR was to answer the two following review questions:

- 1 What is the existing evidence on the effectiveness of RMMs to prevent VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV spread/introduction via movement of eggs, sperm or gametes from a non-free to a free area?
- 2 What are the critical points to be controlled at the establishments where the eggs, sperm and gametes of aquaculture animals are produced to ensure early detection and prevent further spread of VHS, IHN or HPR-deleted ISAV?

The databases search was carried out on 25 October 2024 in MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Scopus. After adding records retrieved through reference list checking and hand searching via Google Scholar and specialized websites, a total 2,454 unique references were identified. From these references, 13 were finally selected, for data extraction. The full selection process is displayed in **Figure A.2**.

The following data was extracted: Study period, Study type (experimental/field), Pathogen (IHNV, VHSV, ISAV), Fish species, Matrice (eggs/sperm/gametes), Intervention type (RMM/critical control point), Intervention description, Sample size, Outcome description, Outcome value, Short conclusion.

FIGURE A.2 PRISMA diagram describing the different steps of SLR 2.

* Records identified through reference list checking and hand searching

A.2.2.2. Results

Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia

Five studies investigated RMMs or critical points to control VHSV.

Four of these studies focused on the evaluation of iodophor disinfection against VHSV.

First, an *in vitro* study demonstrated that a 5min exposure to an organic iodine complexes Wescodyne® or Betadine® at 8 ppm effectively inactivates VHSV in suspension (Initial log 4.5 TCID50/ml) as no viral cytopathic effect observed (Amend and Pietsch 1972).

Tuttle-Lau et al. (2009) showed that iodophor disinfection effectively eliminates VHSV from the surfaces of walleye (*Sander vitreus*) and northern pike (*Esox Lucius*) fertilised eggs. Indeed, VHSV was not isolated from any iodophor-disinfected eggs challenged at 108 PFU/mL, contrarily to control eggs in which the virus was isolated immediately after challenge and for up to 4 days. The authors suggest to apply iodophor disinfection at 100 parts per million immediately (less than 5 min) post fertilisation for 30 min or at 90 min after fertilisation for 10 min, as it will effectively reduce VHSV transmission without affecting egg hatch.

Groocock et al. (2013) tested the effect of iodophor disinfection on experimentally infected walleye fertilised eggs (105 PFU/mL VHSV genotype IVb). This study confirmed that a 30min iodophor treatment disinfects eggs at the 100mg/L dose as detected by viral isolation. However, the 50mg/L dose may be insufficient to destroy VHSV immediately, since the virus could be isolated at one day post infection in eggs that had been disinfected at this later dose. It is mentioned that the virus may be protected by the jelly coating of the eggs or residual tannic acid may mitigate the disinfecting properties of iodophor. The authors recommend disinfection with iodophor at 100 mg/L for 30 min.

Bowzer et al. (2011) quantified the viability of walleye fertilised eggs and growth of larvae that had been treated with iodine after fertilisation as a method for disinfecting potentially contagious gametes. The authors concluded that iodine treatment can be an effective disinfectant against VHSV without compromising survival or growth when walleye fertilised eggs are exposed to 100mg/L iodine for 30 min. However, the study pinpoints that the survival in this study was lower than survival rates reported by other studies that have used more typical exposure durations and iodine concentrations, such as 15 min and 50g/L, respectively.

Additionally, Øye and Rimstad (2001) investigated the effect of ultraviolet irradiation which can be used for treatment of wastewater from hatcheries for instance. VHSV suspended in fresh-water was shown to be very sensitive to UVC irradiation (280–200 nm) as a 99.9% inactivation was reached with an UVC dose of $7.9 \pm 1.5 \text{ J m}^{-2}$.

Infectious haematopoietic necrosis

Six studies investigated RMMs and/or critical points to control IHNV.

Amend and Pietsch (1972) carried out an experiment to study the effect of several disinfectants, such as malachite green and sodium chloride, but only sodium hypochlorite and the iodophor Wescodyne® inactivated completely IHNV in suspension (no viral cytopathic effect observed). The authors then also showed that 5min exposure to organic iodine complexes Wescodyne® or Betadine® at 8–16ppm effectively inactivates IHNV (Initial log 6.8 TCID₅₀/ml). Moreover, they found that the virucidal activity of the disinfectants was not affected by water hardness, but was reduced to a pH above 8 and by the presence of organic matter. Wescodyne® was less affected by these two parameters than Betadine®.

Batts et al. (1991) showed that a 99.9% virus reduction was obtained in 7.5s when IHNV (105 PFU/ml) and iodine (0.1 mg/L) were combined in distilled-deionized or hatchery water. Under the conditions used in this study, inactivation was not affected by temperature, salinity or water hardness. The authors concluded that iodine could be added to the hatchery water supply and would effectively inactivate IHNV without being toxic to fish.

Goldes and Mead (1995) demonstrated that both static and circulating iodine disinfection at 100mg/L during 10min or 60min was efficient to eliminate 99.98% of IHNV ($1.8\text{--}8.5 \times 10^6$ PFU/mL) in rainbow trout fertilised eggs.

Wedemeyer et al. (1978) showed that ozone applied at a rate of 70mg/h/L during 30s–10min depending on the type of water, was sufficient to inactivate IHNV in suspension (104–105 TCID₅₀/ml). Chlorine at 0.5mg/L during 10min was also efficient, even in hard water.

Meyers et al. (1990; 2003) described the impact of the Alaskan Sockeye Salmon Culture Policy (SSCP). The SSCP consists of 1. IHNV-free water (obtained from ultraviolet depuration or from water source without sockeye salmon) is used for incubation and rearing; 2. Stringent disinfection for utensils, facilities, personnel and external surface of broodfish during collection of milt and unfertilised eggs; 3. Eggs from each female or fertilised separately from milt from one or two males that are then discarded, and each egg lot is then separately water-hardened in a 100mg/mL solution of iodophor for 60min 4. fertilised eggs are placed in incubators that allow compartmentalization into small lot size. After the implementation of SSCP in Alaska in 1981, the total losses of juvenile fish attributed to IHNV through 1999 were only 5%, compared to very high levels (45% to 49%) in brood years 1974, 1978, and 1979.

Infection with HPR-deleted infectious salmon anaemia virus

Four studies investigated RMMs and/or critical points to control ISAV.

First, the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety, Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, established an ad hoc group consisting of nine national and international experts to answer a series of questions related to ISA management strategies (Wenche et al., 2007). The majority of the ad hoc group agrees that one of the best-suited targets for screening for the presence of ISAV infection in apparently healthy fish is broodfish by use of real-time RT-PCR. The group recommends the screening of broodfish in the "breeding nucleus" (i.e. source of eggs for production, but also of eggs for the next generation of brood fish), combined with strict biosecurity procedures for handling of broodfish and sexual products. After spawning, the eggs from the breeding nucleus must be kept in separate cylinders, one for each family. This means that progeny from individual parents that have tested positive can be easily discarded. There should be a close disease surveillance of the broodfish. All fish suspected of possessing clinical or pathological changes caused by ISA should be discarded before stripping. Vaccination of fish that will be used as broodfish may also be a possible intervention.

The ad hoc group of experts estimated also that iodophore-based disinfectants is a good method to decontaminate fertilised egg surfaces. However, iodophore disinfection cannot be relied upon to inactivate fully any eventual virus. Iodophore disinfection (100 ppm, 10 min) is normally used after fertilisation, before transportation from brood fish facilities to hatcheries, and often also after arrival at hatcheries. Prophylactic anti-fungal treatment of fertilised eggs with formaldehyde (0.01 %, 10-30 min) is used routinely several times per week prior to the eyed egg stage in areas where the water quality is not optimal. Such treatment would be expected to inactivate ISA virus since 0.5 % formalin (which equals 0.02 % formaldehyde) inactivates free ISA virus.

Then, Smail et al. (2004) evaluated the in vitro efficacy of iodophors, chloramine-T, chlorine dioxide, and peracetic acid/acetic acid/hydrogen peroxide mixture as disinfectants against ISAV suspension. All the disinfectants tested produced a titre reduction of $>4 \log_{10}$ ffu/ml which is the DEFRA standard for approved disinfectants under the UK Animal Health Act (1981). All disinfectants were found suitable at the following doses for 5 min contact time: iodophors at 100 ppm, chloramine T at 1% w/v, chlorine dioxide at 100 ppm, peracetic acid/hydrogen peroxide/acetic acid mixture at 0.02–0.06% peracetic acid/0.08–0.25% hydrogen peroxide/0.04–0.13% acetic acid.

Øye and Rimstad (2001) studied the effect of UVC irradiation on ISAV suspended in fresh water, and concluded that the virus is very sensitive to UVC, with a 99.9% inactivation when exposed to a dose of $33 \pm 3.5 \text{ J m}^{-2}$.

Last, Liltved et al. (2006) showed that ISAV was sensitive to both UV irradiation and ozonated seawater. A 99.9% inactivation of the virus was obtained with an UV dose of 7.7 mJ/cm^2 and 90% reductions in virus titers were obtained by C T values (the product of total residual oxidants concentration and contact time) of 1.4 (mg s)/l .

A.2.2.3. Discussion and conclusion

The success of such programs as the SSCP implemented in 1981 in Alaska to control IHNV (Meyers et al. 1990, Meyers et al., 2003) or the ISAV control measures used in the Norwegian salmon egg production industry (Rimstad et al., 2006) demonstrates that multiple interventions aiming to mitigate VHSV, IHNV or HPR-deleted ISAV transmission via fertilised eggs or sperm should be applied at each step of the production process. These measures should be able to detect infections early on to prevent pathogens from spreading down the production line.

Broodstock

Prevention of virus presence in gametes and fertilised eggs starts with the broodstock. Utilizing pathogen-free broodstock is a widely acknowledged method for preventing vertically transmitted diseases (Winton, 1991; Brock and Bullis, 2001; Dixon et al., 2016). However, maintaining broodfish free from pathogens is not always feasible in areas where the pathogens are endemic. Pathogen-free stock, screening and removal of infected broodstock are key strategies applied to broodstock and are also recommended by WOA (Brock and Bullis, 2001; WOA, 2024). Most experts from the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety concurred that screening broodfish for ISAV infection using real-time RT-PCR is one of the most effective strategies for identifying infections in healthy fish (Rimstad et al., 2006). Similarly, in Japan, systematic health checks of broodstock are carried out to ensure that the fish are free from certain key pathogens. Specialized diagnostic methods and regular inspections are necessary to create broodstock that is specific pathogen free (Yoshimizu, 2009).

Separation of fish in different production phases in dedicated areas

The definition of specific, segregated production areas is an essential aspect of disease management in aquaculture. Kasai and Nishikawa (2018) mentioned that individual broodstock should ideally be separated during fertilisation and reared in separate containers until the broodstock is certified as pathogen-free. By doing this, if a positive sample is detected, only the infected lot is contained and eliminated. In the Alaskan SSCP, each egg lot is separately water-hardened and eggs are then placed in incubators that allow separation into small lot sizes.

Fertilised eggs and milt

Another essential mitigation measure consists in the disinfection of egg surfaces. Our SLR findings indicate that most of the existing research on mitigation measures is focused on iodophor disinfection. Indeed, this method has been widely used since the 1970s to minimize the spread of viral pathogens linked to eggs or sperm. It is used after egg fertilisation, before transportation from brood fish facilities to hatcheries, and often also after arrival at hatcheries (Rimstad et al., 2006; Winton, 1991). Both field and experimental studies have demonstrated that iodine compounds, recommended for the disinfection of salmonid fertilised eggs, can efficiently reduce the transmission of the viruses of interest (Amend and Pietsch, 1972; Goldes and Mead, 1995; Meyers et al., 2003; Rimstad et al., 2006; Tuttle-Lau et al., 2009; Grocock et al., 2013). Moreover, it was shown that iodine treatment didn't compromise the survival or growth of eggs (Bowzer et al., 2011). Nevertheless, there is also some evidence of infection in progeny of infected broodstock despite disinfection of the egg surface (Ratliff et al., 1982; Mulcahy & Bauersfeld, 1983; Yoshimizu et al., 1989; Winton, 1991; Goldes & Mead, 1995; Dixon et al., 2016). It is suggested that viral titres may have been so high in ovarian fluid that disinfection protocols were insufficient, and also that a small proportion of virions might have been concealed in the irregular surface of the egg membrane and thus inaccessible to the iodophor (Goldes & Mead, 1995; Dixon et al., 2016). Furthermore, timing of disinfection in relation to egg activation (hardening) can influence the outcome of disinfection, because during the activation of the egg the surface changes considerably (Winton, 1991; Bovo et al., 2005; Rimstad et al., 2006). Last, the possibility of true vertical transmission of the viruses in some rare cases has not been totally ruled out (cf. Section 1. SLR1: Risk of true vertical transmission). However, while fertilised egg disinfection with iodophors might not be completely effective, it significantly lowers the risk of transmission of the pathogens of interest and is so far the best available disinfectant for fertilised egg surfaces, and is commonly implemented in numerous production facilities (Brock and Bullis, 2001; Rimstad et al., 2006; Dixon et al., 2016). The current WOA recommendations for surface disinfection of salmonid eggs at hatcheries is indeed to use iodophores, such as povidone-iodine solutions (100 ppm for a minimum of 10 minutes)

and subsequent incubation in virus-free water (WOAH, 2024). These recommendations take into account conditions that enhance the effectiveness of this protocol, by applying it only to hardened newly fertilised or eyed eggs, rinsing eggs in pathogen-free saline to remove organic matter before, and maintaining the pH of the iodophore solution between 6 and 8. Lastly, other disinfectants such as malachite green and formalin have also been used in the past for disinfecting fertilised eggs, but have been shown to be less effective than iodophors (Amend and Pietsch, 1972; Bovo et al., 2005; Rimstad et al., 2006).

A recent qualitative risk assessment on the risk of transmission of infectious disease through trade of cryopreserved milt (Espen Rimstad et al., 2019) reported that there is no effective disinfection procedures for fish seminal fluids described in the literature. Thus, the pathogens, which could originate from the brood fish or from contamination following stripping, may be present in frozen milt. However, the report mentions also that the primary practical application of salmonid milt is for the fertilisation of salmonid eggs, which are typically subjected to a disinfection procedure.

Water

Since VHSV, IHNV and ISAV are all able to survive in water (Bovo et al., 2005; Rimstad et al., 2006), maintaining pathogen-free water for incubation and rearing is another a key factor for controlling the diseases (Meyers et al., 1990; Dixon et al., 2016). Common disinfectants used to treat water in aquaculture applications include UV light, chlorine or ozone, which all have been shown to be effective to produce virus-free water in laboratory settings (Wedemeyer et al., 1978; Brock and Bullis, 2001; Øye & Rimstad, 2001; Liltved et al., 2006). However, Bovo et al. (2005) report problems occurring in field trials due to mechanical and electrical failures that occur routinely with equipment that must deliver a compound at a virus inactivating dose that is non-toxic to the fish.

In conclusion, the outcomes derived from the current SLR emphasize the need for executing a comprehensive set of preventive and control strategies at the various stages of the fertilised egg and sperm production processes. There is evidence that this combination of measures can effectively mitigate the risk of transmitting VHSV, IHNV and HPR-deleted ISAV via the movement of fertilised eggs or sperm from a non-free to a free area.

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